

ECONOMICS OF PRODUCTION OF SELECTED COLE VEGETABLES IN NAGPUR DISTRICT.

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Abstract

Cole vegetables are the most important contributor in cultivated vegetable. Among the different vegetable grown in India cole vegetables contributed good in both Regional and National income. India is second largest global producer of cole vegetable after China. The present study was undertaken in Nagpur district of Vidarbha region of state Maharashtra. Cabbage and cauliflower were selected for the present study. Out of fourteen tahsils in Nagpur district, two tahsils namely Katol and Narkhed were selected purposively having maximum area and production of cole vegetables. Five villages were selected from each tehsil and 10 farmers were selected from each villages purposively. A list of all the selected vegetable growers of the selected villages were prepared from consolidated list of selected vegetable growers, total 100 vegetable growers have been selected randomly (50 growers for cabbage and 50 growers for cauliflowers). The per hectare total cost of cultivation at Cost C₃ for cabbage and cauliflower was Rs. 86394.56 and Rs. 90793.83 respectively. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for cabbage and cauliflower was 1.55 and 1.62 respectively. The study indicates that cultivation of cabbage and cauliflower were economically profitable.

Keywords: Cabbage, Cauliflower, Cost and Returns, input-output ratio, Profitable

Introduction

Cole Vegetables play an significant role in total cultivated vegetables regarding production and income of farmers. These crops are generally short duration hence more than one crop can be raised on the basis of early, medium and late duration varieties. In India, cole vegetable crops are generally grown in open fields therefore the cost of cultivation is less as compared to protected cultivation as followed in the Western Countries. Cole vegetables are the vital sources of minerals, vitamins and dietary fibers and play an important role in supplying nutrition to human health. Cole vegetables play an important role in the household nutritional security, employment generation and alleviation of hunger. According to (FAO-2022-23), India rank second in cabbage and cauliflower production. In India West Bengal ranks first in Cabbage and Cauliflower production (NHB- 2022-23).

Materials and Methods

Cost A₁: All actual expenses incurred in production by producer. The following items are included in cost A₁

1. Value of Hired human labour (HL)
2. Value of hired and owned bullock labour (BL)
3. Value of hired and owned machine labour (ML)
4. Value of seeds
5. Value of insecticides and pesticides
6. Value of manures
7. Value of fertilizers
8. Irrigation charges
9. Depreciation on implements and farm building
10. Land revenue, cesses and other taxes
11. Interest on working capital
12. Miscellaneous expenses

Cost A₂ : Cost A₁ + Rent paid for leased-in land

Cost B₁ : Cost A₁ + interest value of owned fixed capital assets

Cost B₂ : Cost B₁ + rental value of owned land

Cost C₁ : Cost B₁ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₂ : Cost B₂+ imputed value of family labour

Cost C₃ : Cost C₂ + 10 per cent of Cost C₂ on account of managerial functions performed by farmers.

Gross and net returns**Gross returns**

Gross returns of the farmers under the present study was estimated from returns obtained from sale of main produce.

Gross returns = Value of main produce + Value of by produce

Net returns

Net returns was computed at different costs i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by deducting respective costs from the gross returns.

Input- output ratio

It is ratio between the value of gross output and the cost of cultivation at different cost. The input output ratio was worked out with reference to cost A₁, A₂, B₁, B₂, C₁, C₂ and C₃. The importance of working input output ratio with reference to cost was taken on in to account to judge the efficiency of farm input.

Results and Discussion**Cost of Cultivation of selected cabbage and cauliflower growers**

An analysis of cost would enable the farmers to re-examine the utilization of farm resources effectively. Various cost concepts such as cost A₁, A₂, B₁, B₂, C₁, C₂ and C₃. were estimated.

Cost and returns in Cabbage

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cabbage growers were workout and presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Per hectare cost of cultivation of selected cabbage growers (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Unit/Ha		Input/Ha	Cost per Input (Rs.)	Total Cost Rs.)	Percentage to total cost C ₃
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	21.97	300.00	6591.00	7.63
		Female	Days	54.74	200.00	10948.00	12.67
		Total				17539.00	20.30
2	Bullock Labour		Days	8.74	700.00	6118.00	7.08
3	Machine Charges		Hrs	2.84	900.00	2556.00	2.96
4	Manure		CL	5.31	500.00	2655.00	3.07
5	Seeds		Gm	0.64	21000.00	13440.00	15.56

		N	Kg	147.9	6.02	890.35	1.03
6	Fertilizer	P	Kg	51.05	11.21	572.27	0.66
		Total				1462.62	1.69
7	Irrigation Charges		Rs.			1429.00	1.65
8	Plant protection		Rs.			3291.09	3.81
9	Incidental Charges		Rs.			51.00	0.06
10	Repairing Charges		Rs.			390.97	0.45
11	Working Capital (1 to 10)		Rs.			48932.68	56.64
12	Int. on working capital @ 6% per annum		Rs.			2935.96	3.40
13	Depreciation		Rs.			421.09	0.49
14	Land revenue		Rs.			45.07	0.05
15	Cost A₁ (11 to 14)					52334.81	60.58
16	Rental value of leased in land					-	-
17	Cost A₂ (15 to 16)					52334.81	60.58
18	Int.on fix. capital @ 10% per annum					1463.70	1.69
19	Cost B₁ (15 +18)					53798.51	62.27
20	Rental value of land					14637.00	16.94
21	Cost B₂ (19 to 20)					68435.51	79.21
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	16.61	300.00	4983.00	5.77
		Female	Days	25.61	200.00	5122.00	5.93
		Total				10105.00	11.70
23	Cost C₁ (19 +22)					63903.51	73.97
24	Cost C₂ (21+22)					78540.51	90.91
25	10% of Cost C ₂					7854.05	9.09
26	Cost C₃ (24+25)					86394.56	100
27	Yield Per Hectare	Main	qtls	146.09	914.10	133540.86	
29	Per qtl. Cost of production					591.38	

(Figures in parentheses indicates the percentages to cost C₃)

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cabbage was workout and presented in Table 1. It is revealed that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of cabbage at cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂ and cost C₃ were Rs. 52334.81, 52334.81, Rs. 53798.51, Rs. 68435.51, Rs. 63903.51, Rs. 78540.51 and Rs. 86394.56 respectively. At cost 'A₁' share of seed was 15.56 per cent, hired human labour 20.30 per cent, bullock labour 7.08 per cent, manure 3.07 per cent, fertilizers 1.69 per cent, indicating that all the above inputs were cash inputs. The

cost 'B₁' contributes to 62.27 per cent, cost 'B₂' contribute 79.21 per cent. The share of family labour was 11.70 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by cabbage growers was 146.09 quintals with gross returns of Rs. 133540.86.

Costs and Returns in Cauliflower

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cauliflower growers were workout and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Per hectare cost of cultivation of selected cauliflower growers (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Unit/Ha		Input/Ha	Cost per	Total Cost (Rs)	Percentage to total Cost C ₃
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	23.26	300.00	6978.00	7.69
		Female	Days	56.56	200.00	11312.00	12.46
		Total				18290.00	20.14
2	Bullock Labour		Days	8.74	670.00	5855.80	6.45
3	Machine Charges		Hours	2.84	920.00	2612.80	2.88
4	Manure		CL	5.31	480.00	2548.80	2.81
5	Seeds		Gms	0.62	21050.00	13051.00	14.37
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg	104.15	5.96	620.73	0.68
		P	Kg	55.05	11.21	617.11	0.68
		Total				1237.84	1.36
7	Irrigation Charges		Rs.			1320.00	1.45
8	Plant protection		Rs.			3918.36	4.32
9	Incidental Charges		Rs.			45.04	0.05
10	Repairing Charges		Rs.			367.34	0.40
11	Working Capital (1 to 10)		Rs.			49246.98	54.24
12	Int. on working capital @ 6%		Rs.			2954.82	3.25
13	Depreciation		Rs.			579.00	0.64
14	Land revenue		Rs.			85.04	0.09
15	Cost A₁ (11 to 14)					52865.84	58.23
16	Rental value of leased in land					-	-
17	Cost A₂ (15 to 16)					52865.84	58.23

18	Int.on fix. capital @ 10% /annum					1735.00	1.91
19	Cost B₁ (15 +18)					54600.84	60.14
20	Rental value of land					15923.00	17.54
21	Cost B₂ (19 to 20)					70523.84	77.67
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	21.04	300.00	6312.00	6.95
		Female	Days	28.52	200.00	5704.00	6.28
		Total				12016.00	13.23
23	Cost C₁ (19 +22)					66616.84	73.37
24	Cost C₂ (21+22)					82539.84	90.91
25	10% of Cost C ₂					8253.98	9.09
26	Cost C₃ (24+25)					90793.83	100.00
27	Yield Per Hectare	Main	Qtls.	135.07	1089.00	147091.23	
29	Per qtl. Cost of production					672.20	

(Figures in parentheses indicates the percentages to total cost C₃)

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cauliflower was worked out and presented in Table 2. It is revealed that the per hectare cost of cultivation of cauliflower at cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂ and cost C₃ were Rs. 52865.84, Rs. 52865.84, Rs. 54600.84, Rs. 70523.84, Rs. 66616.84, Rs. 82539.84 and Rs. 90793.83 respectively. In cost 'A₁' share of seed was 14.37 per cent, hired human labour 20.14 per cent, bullock labour 6.45 per cent, manure 2.81 per cent, fertilizers 1.36 per cent, indicating that all the above inputs are cash inputs. The hired human labour share highest among them in Cost

Table 3. Per hectare cost, returns from cabbage and cauliflower

Sr.No	Input	Cabbage	Cauliflower
1	Yield (q/ha)	146.09	135.07
2	Gross returns (Rs.)	133540.86	147091.23
	Value of main produce (Rs.)	133540.86	147091.23
3	Costs (Rs.)		
	COST A ₁	52334.81	52865.84
	COST A ₂	52334.81	52865.84
	COST B ₁	53798.51	54600.84
	COST B ₂	68435.51	70523.84
	COST C ₁	63903.51	66616.84
	COST C ₂	78540.51	82539.84
	COST C ₃	86394.56	90793.83
4	Net Returns (Rs.)		
	COST A ₁	81206.06	94225.39
	COST A ₂	81206.06	94225.39
	COST B ₁	79742.36	92490.39
	COST B ₂	65105.35	76567.39
	COST C ₁	69637.36	80474.39
	COST C ₂	55000.35	64551.39
	COST C ₃	47146.31	56297.40
5	Input-Output ratio		
	COST A ₁	2.55	2.78
	COST A ₂	2.55	2.78
	COST B ₁	2.48	2.69
	COST B ₂	1.95	2.09
	COST C ₁	2.09	2.21
	COST C ₂	1.70	1.78
	COST C ₃	1.55	1.62

A₁. The cost 'B₁' contributes to 60.14 per cent, cost 'B₂' contribute 77.67 per cent. The share of family labour was 13.23 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by cauliflower growers was 135.07 quintals with gross returns of Rs. 147091.23.

Per hectare cost, returns and profitability from cabbage and cauliflower

The per hectare cost and returns of the cabbage and cauliflower was worked out are presented in Table 3.

The Table 3. indicates that per hectare production of vegetables for cabbage and cauliflower growers were 146.09 and 135.07 quintals respectively. The gross returns from cabbage and cauliflower were Rs. 133540.86 and Rs.147091.23 respectively. Whereas the cost of cultivation at C₃ of cabbage and cauliflower crops have been estimated to be Rs. 86394.56, and Rs. 90793.83 respectively. The per hectare net returns at cost C₃ received by cabbage and cauliflower growers were Rs. 47146.31 and Rs. 56297.30 respectively. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for cabbage and cauliflower growers were 1.55 and 1.62 respectively.

Conclusion

The average yield of cabbage and cauliflower was 146.09 qt/ha and 135.07 qt/ha respectively. It is observed that per hectare cost of cultivation of cabbage and cauliflower at cost C₃ was Rs. 86394.56 and Rs. 90793.83 respectively. The gross returns from cabbage and cauliflower was Rs.133540.86 and Rs. 147091.23 respectively. The average yield (Rs/ha) from cabbage and cauliflower was Rs. 47146.31 and Rs. 56297.40 respectively. The average yield and gross returns per hectare increased with the increase in size of farms. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for cabbage and cauliflower was 1:1.55 and 1:1.62 respectively. This indicate that, cultivation of cabbage and cauliflower were economically profitable.

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